

From directive to practice: mapping national frameworks for RECs and CECs under RED III and IME III *

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Abstract. This research sets out a comparative methodology intended to assess the extent to which selected EU Member States – namely, Austria, Belgium (Flanders), Denmark, France and Germany – have incorporated the concepts of Renewable Energy Communities (RECs), Citizen Energy Communities (CECs), and related models, into national law. The analysis draws on the Energy Communities Repository and country-specific legislation, and identifies variations in legal definitions, eligible participants, energy types, spatial requirements, and energy sharing provisions. The objective of this study is to provide a structured comparison of national frameworks in light of the revised Renewable Energy Directive (RED III) and the Internal Market for Electricity Directive (IME III). The analysis will identify both regulatory gaps and enabling mechanisms.

Keywords: Comparative energy law, Energy Communities Repository, EU energy directives, RED III and IME III implementation

1 Introduction

This document sets out a comparative methodology for assessing the implementation of the concept of energy communities within the national legal frameworks of selected EU Member States. This implementation is measured in accordance with the revised Renewable Energy Directive (RED III) and the Internal Market for Electricity Directive (IME III). The analysis draws on the Energy Communities Repository policy database and national regulations, with a focus on Austria, Belgium (Flanders), Denmark, France and Germany—countries identified as early movers in operationalising the energy community provisions.

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The approach involves the systematic extraction and comparison of legal definitions, eligible actors, permitted energy types and activities, spatial and grid connection constraints, and ownership or governance requirements. This text focuses on the existence of frameworks that facilitate electricity and heat sharing. This synthesis provides a structured overview of national adaptations and highlights key divergences in the scope, ambition, and implementation pathways for energy communities across Member States.

2 Methodology

To analyse the current status of the implementation of RED III and the IME III in terms of the adoption of the energy communities concept by EU members, the Energy Communities Repository [1] policy database and local regulations of Austria, Germany, Denmark, Belgium (Flanders) and France were consulted. These countries were selected because they have taken the first steps towards implementing the EC concept [2]. The database within the repository provides information on the status of implementation and the regulations issued to adopt the Energy Communities concept for all EU members up to the year 2023. The database was also used to compare the types of concepts adopted and the legal forms, types of energy, activities, members, connection and proximity requirements, and ownership rules permitted.

3 Results

3.1 Analysis of EU member adoption of energy communities

The following section will show the extent to which regulations for energy sharing and heat sharing already exist in the individual countries analysed. Austria, Germany, Denmark, Belgium (Flanders) and France were analysed for this purpose. The first step is to examine the extent to which the individual countries have definitions for the various legal forms through which energy sharing can function - namely RECs, CECs and the jointly acting self-consumer in the field of renewable electricity. In a second step, an overview is provided of the regulatory framework in the individual countries for the different forms of implementation.

Germany: Legal and regulatory framework for energy communities and energy sharing In Germany, the only legally binding definition of an energy community is found in § 3 No. 15 of the Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG) (see appendix A), as amended in 2023 (Energy Communities Repository, Germany, p. 3) [3]. The term *Bürgerenergiegesellschaft* is translated as “citizen energy community” (CEC) in the legal text. However, since Germany aimed to transpose the concept of Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) under EU law, the term REC is used in the following discussion. According to § 3 No. 15 EEG, a REC is defined as a cooperative or other type of company

meeting specific requirements: it must comprise at least 50 natural persons with voting rights. Additionally, at least 75% of those voting rights must be held by individuals registered under the Federal Registration Act as residing within a postal code area that lies wholly or partly within a 50-kilometre radius of the planned installation. For solar installations, this distance is measured from the outer edge of the system; for wind turbines, from the centre of the tower. Moreover, German law does not provide any alternative legal definition for either RECs or CECs.

With regard to jointly acting self-suppliers, German law provides two implementation models: the tenant electricity model (Section 42a EnWG) and joint building supply (Section 42b EnWG). Both fall under the definition of "customer installations" as set out in Section 3 No. 2a EnWG, which means that they operate with their own internal grid infrastructure, independent of the public electricity network.

As previously mentioned in the first paragraph of this subsection, the primary legal framework for regulating citizens' energy initiatives can be found in the EEG, focusing exclusively on photovoltaic (PV) systems and wind turbines. RECs that operate onshore wind turbines with a capacity of up to 18 MW are exempt from participating in competitive tenders, as outlined in § 22b EEG. One requirement for this exemption is that the Federal Network Agency must be notified that the installation qualifies as a REC project (Section 22b (1) No. 1 EEG). Similar provisions apply to PV systems operated by a REC, as stipulated in § 22b (2) EEG.

A key feature of RECs in Germany is that they are purely citizen-owned generation facilities. This means that while participating citizens can generate and sell electricity, they are not permitted to consume the electricity produced by their own systems (as stated in § 3 No. 15b) from EEG, see appendix A).

Currently, German law lacks specific provisions for energy sharing that utilises the public electricity grid. However, such regulations are expected to be implemented by 17 July 2026 as part of the electricity market reform mandated by EU legislation ³.

Beyond the existing legal framework, there are no further regulations. However, this does not imply that other forms of energy sharing are prohibited. Rather, actors must currently be treated in the same way as conventional electricity producers, suppliers, and consumers within the German electricity market. As a result, there are currently no incentives in place to promote new models of energy sharing.

³ As mentioned in Art. 3 No. 1 from Directive (EU/2024/1711) see appendix A.

Legal and regulatory framework for energy communities and energy sharing, in Austria, Belgium (Flanders), Denmark and France.

– Austria:

Austria has implemented targeted policy and regulatory measures to support the development of energy communities. A central initiative is the establishment of the Coordination Centre for Energy Communities (COEC)⁴, which assists stakeholders in setting up and operating energy communities and facilitates their integration into the energy market. In addition, Austria has published a financing guide for renewable energy communities, offering practical support for the formation of such initiatives [1].

Austrian energy law distinguishes between three types of energy communities: Community Generation Plants, Renewable Energy Communities (RECs), and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs). These definitions are codified in the Electricity Industry and Organization Act (EIWOG) (see appendix A). According to Section 7 no. 23a EIWOG, community generation plants are power generation units designed to cover the electricity needs of participating authorized parties. Section 7 no. 6a defines a general energy community as a legal entity that generates, consumes, stores, or sells electricity, operates in the field of aggregation, or provides energy services, and is controlled by its members or shareholders pursuant to Section 16b (3) EIWOG.

RECs, as defined in Section 7 no. 15a EIWOG, are legal entities that enable the joint use of electricity generated within the community. Their members or shareholders must be located in close geographical proximity to each other, in accordance with Section 16c (2) EIWOG.

The legal frameworks for these three forms—Community Generation Plants, Renewable Energy Communities, and Citizen Energy Communities—are set out in both EIWOG and the Renewable Expansion Act (EAG) (see appendix A). Starting with Section 16a EIWOG, the respective community types are addressed in detail: Section 16a governs community generation plants, Section 16b addresses citizen energy communities, and Section 16c regulates renewable energy communities. Sections 16d and 16e contain cross-cutting provisions applicable to all forms of joint energy usage.

Under Section 16a EIWOG, multiple parties are permitted to jointly operate a renewable electricity generation facility and consume the electricity generated. The legal provisions specific to Renewable Energy Communities are laid out in Sections 79 et seq. of the EAG. According to Section 79 (1) EAG, a REC may generate, consume, store, or sell electricity from renewable sources. It may also engage in aggregation and provide additional

⁴ See <https://compass.r2m.cloud/incentives/austrian-coordination-office-for-energy-communities/>

energy services. As per Section 79 (2) EAG, a REC must include at least two members or shareholders and may be composed of natural persons, municipalities, public bodies (in relation to local services), or small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Legally, RECs must take the form of an association, cooperative, partnership, corporation, or similar legal entity with independent legal personality.

Section 80 EAG further provides for financial support schemes for RECs, offering incentives that facilitate their formation and development. The rules governing Citizen Energy Communities are found in Section 16b ElWOG. According to paragraph 1, a CEC may generate, consume, store, or sell electricity. Paragraph 2 allows natural persons, legal entities, and municipalities to participate as members or shareholders. In accordance with paragraph 3, a CEC must be composed of at least two members and be structured as a legal entity with its own legal personality—such as an association, cooperative, partnership, or corporation.

A notable distinction from Germany’s RECs is that Austrian RECs are not limited to electricity. The wording of § 79 EAG permits the use of renewable energy and is not limited to specific types of energy, such as electricity [4].

– **Belgium (Flanders):**

Belgium’s federal structure divides responsibilities across three regions—Wallonia, Flanders, and the Brussels-Capital Region—each of which holds independent authority over energy consumption and the promotion of renewable energy. As a result, the implementation of RECs and CECs falls within the remit of the individual regions, necessitating the development of region-specific regulatory frameworks. This section focuses on the Flemish Region.

In Flanders, the definition of a REC is set out in § 1 of Article 4.8.2 of the Energy Decree (see appendix A). A REC is defined as a legal entity founded on the principles of open and voluntary participation by its shareholders or members, whose primary objective is to deliver environmental, economic, or social benefits to these participants or to the wider environment in which it operates. Profit generation is either not pursued or subordinated to the community’s overarching purpose. Similarly, Article 4.8.1 § 1 from the Energy Decree defines a CEC as a legal entity based on open and voluntary participation, which aims primarily to provide environmental, economic, or social benefits to its members, associates, or the environment, and not to maximize profit. These communities are authorized to carry out a range of energy-related activities as outlined in Article 4.8.4 § 1 from the Energy Decree. The biggest difference between RECs and CECs in Flanders is that RECs can only use renewable energy, while CECs can use all types of energy, including fossil fuels.

The Flemish Energy Decree further regulates the composition and functioning of these communities. The regulations on CECs and RECs are very similar. According to § 1, third sentence, of Article 4.8.2, participants in a REC must be natural persons, local authorities, or SMEs, whose involvement in the energy community does not constitute their main commercial or professional activity. Unlike CECs, they must be located in close geographical proximity to the renewable energy installations operated by the REC. Participation is also conditioned upon connection to an electricity distribution network, the local transmission network, a closed electricity distribution network, or a district heating or cooling network. This regulatory framework explicitly allows RECs to share thermal energy in addition to electricity.

– **Denmark:**

Denmark has a long-standing tradition of citizen participation in the energy sector. For several decades, electricity generation companies have been largely consumer-owned, often organised as cooperatives or operated by municipalities. A similar structure characterises the district heating sector, where many facilities are either consumer cooperatives or municipally owned utilities (from (Energy Communities Repository, Denmark, p. 3 [3]).

In terms of legal definitions, Denmark recognises both RECs and CECs. These are governed primarily by the Danish Consolidated Act (LBK no. 1791 of 02 September 2021 and (LBK n°984 of 12 May 2021, Ministry of Climate, Energy and Supply, The Electricity Supply Act) (see appendix A, and the Executive Order BEK no. 1069 of 30 May 2021 (see appendix A. According to this framework, a REC is defined as a legal entity based on open and voluntary participation, operating independently and effectively controlled by members or investors who are located near the renewable energy projects managed by the entity. Eligible participants include natural persons, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and local public authorities such as municipalities. The primary objective of a REC is not economic gain, but rather to deliver environmental, economic, or social benefits to its participants or the local community.

The definition of CECs under § 4 of BEK no. 1069 is similar in its emphasis on voluntary and open participation, but CECs must be controlled exclusively by natural persons, municipalities, local authorities, or small enterprises. Unlike RECs, any type of legal or natural person may join a CEC, but the controlling influence must remain with eligible entities. Members of CECs are also subject to the same restrictions on commercial scale and influence as REC members. Importantly, while RECs require geographical proximity between participants and the renewable energy installation, CEC members may be supplied with electricity even if they are not located near the production facilities (§ 12 (2) of BEK n°1069).

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From a regulatory standpoint, the legal framework governing RECs and CECs is largely unified under BEK no. 1069. As such, both types are often collectively referred to as Energy Communities (ECs) in Danish legal and policy discourse. Notably, current regulations apply solely to the electricity sector; there are no specific provisions for the inclusion of heat supply within the scope of ECs (Energy communities Repository, Denmark).

Participants in ECs retain their rights as household consumers and active customers. According to § 8 of BEK no. 1069, ECs are permitted to engage in a broad range of activities including electricity generation, consumption, aggregation, energy storage, supply, energy efficiency services, and the operation of electric vehicle charging infrastructure. However, they are not authorised to own or operate electricity distribution grids (from Energy communities Repository, Denmark, p. 5 [3]).

In terms of market access, § 10 of BEK no. 1069 grants ECs non-discriminatory access to all electricity markets, either directly or through third-party arrangements. To participate, ECs are required to establish an electricity trading or aggregator entity. Once established, ECs must be treated in a fair and proportionate manner in their roles as consumers, producers, or energy service providers, as stipulated in § 11 of the Executive Order.

– **France:**

France has had a regulatory framework for energy sharing in place since 2016 [?], which is reflected in Ordinance No. 2021-236 of 3 March 2021 (see appendix A). Definitions and provisions governing access to support schemes were amended by Law No. 2023-175 of 10 March 2023⁵. The French law provides definitions for both Renewable Energy Communities (RECs)

⁵ Title XI - Energy communities and participative investment of the Energy Code, created by Ordinance n° 2021-236 of 3 March 2021 and modified by the Law n° 2023-175 of 10 March 2023 related to the acceleration of the production of renewable energies. Available at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/jorf/id/JORFTEXT000043210210/> on the acceleration of renewable energy production (Energy Communities Repository, France, p.3)

and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs). Collectively, these are referred to as Energy Communities (ECs), for which certain shared provisions apply. Additionally, the French law contains rules governing so-called “citizen energy projects,” which are based on governance models that enable control by citizens and local authorities [3].

According to Article L. 291-1 of the French Energy Code ⁶, a REC is defined as a legal entity with open and voluntary membership. It must be autonomous in the sense of Article 3 and Annex I of the European Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC on the definition of micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises. The objective of a REC is to provide environmental, economic, or social benefits to its shareholders, members, or the local areas where it operates—rather than to generate financial profits. Members of a REC may include natural persons, mixed economy companies (i.e., *Société d’économie mixte*) with both public and private capital, and associations whose members may include natural persons, SMEs, local authorities and their groupings, and mixed economy companies.

According to Article L. 292-1 of the Energy Code, a CEC is defined as a legal entity with open and voluntary participation of any type of member or shareholder. Like RECs, CECs must also be autonomous in accordance with Recommendation 2003/361/EC of the European Commission. Furthermore, CECs aim to provide environmental, economic, or social benefits to their members, shareholders, or the local areas in which they operate, rather than seeking financial profit. Articles L. 291-1, L. 292-2, and L. 291-4 of the Energy Code also contain common provisions applicable to both RECs and CECs.

From a regulatory perspective, it is particularly important that RECs are permitted to produce, consume, store, and sell renewable energy, including via Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs). They must have non-discriminatory access to all relevant energy markets, either directly or through aggregation (Article L. 291-2 of the Energy Code). Moreover, RECs engaging in energy sharing must preserve the rights and obligations of their members as customers (Article L. 291-2 of the Energy Code). The sharing of energy falls under the legal framework for individual and collective self-consumption (CSC), which is governed by Articles L. 315-1 to L. 315-8 of the Energy Code.

In France, CSC refers to the supply of electricity between one or more producers and one or more final consumers who are bound together within a legal entity, with the injection and withdrawal points located in the same building or residential complex. By default, the geographical scope

⁶ The Energy Code (consolidated version) https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/texte_lc/LEGITEXT000023983208?init=true&page=1&query=L.+291-1&searchField=ALL&tab_selection=all

is limited to the building level connected to the low or medium voltage distribution grid. However, this scope can be extended to a 2 km radius between the most distant production and consumption points, provided the total generation capacity does not exceed 3 MW and all connection points are on the low-voltage grid. In exceptional cases—subject to approval by the competent ministry, taking into account the remoteness of the site, dispersed settlement patterns, or low population density—this scope can be extended up to 20 km (in rural locations with lower population density).

From a financial perspective, CSC schemes may benefit from specific network tariffs designed by the Distribution System Operator (DSO), ensuring that participants do not pay access fees that are disproportionate to the actual costs incurred by the grid operator (Article L. 315-3 of the Energy Code).

With regard to CECs, it is important to note that they are also permitted to engage in electricity generation (including from renewable sources), supply, aggregation, storage, and sales. CECs may also participate in energy sharing, provided that the rights and obligations of final consumers are respected (Article L. 292-2 of the Energy Code). In this respect, the same rules apply to RECs and CECs, with the difference that CECs are restricted to electricity sharing only (Article L. 292-2 of the Energy Code).

In summary, it can be observed that the regulatory frameworks for energy sharing differ across countries. While heat sharing is typically not explicitly addressed, it is also not expressly excluded in certain jurisdictions, such as Austria or Belgium (Flanders). Accordingly, it may be inferred that the legal frameworks in these regions at least do not prohibit heat sharing.

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